

INFLUENCE OF GLASS FIBER SIZING ON FIBER/MATRIX ADHESION AND CONSEQUENCES ON SURFACE ASPECT OF SMC COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Feuillade V¹, Bergeret A¹, Quantin J-C¹, Crespy A², Metra C³

- 1) *Ecole des Mines d'Alès, Centre des Matériaux de Grande Diffusion, 6 avenue de Clavières, 30319 Alès Cedex, France*
- 2) *Université de Toulon et du Var, Bâtiment R118, BP 132, 83957 La Garde Cedex, France*
- 3) *Saint-Gobain Vetrotex International, 767 quai des Allobroges, BP 929, 73009 Chambéry Cedex, France*

SUMMARY : Sheet Molding Compound (SMC) is a thermosetting composite material, consisting of a crosslinked unsaturated polyester/styrene matrix combined with short, randomly distributed glass reinforcing fibers. A growing application of SMC is in the automotive industry, where compression molded SMC can be used as exterior body panels. SMC is a good candidate to replace steel panels because of its relatively low cost for volume production, good stiffness and design flexibility. But it is currently very difficult to simultaneously produce homogeneous panels with both the required surface quality (so called Class A) and high production rates. Surface defects are not clearly identified and are difficult to qualify. Their formation mechanisms are not yet clearly established. Thus, in spite of numerous studies in this area, the industries involved require a better understanding.

In the present work, it was decided to focus the study on the influence of the material formulation and its consequences on the surface aspect of SMC panels. Individual characteristics of each component and their interactions play important roles on the processing of SMC paste and on final product properties, such as surface aspect and uniformity. Two of these characteristics are fiber wetting by the resin and fiber/matrix adhesion. Moreover, the SMC process requires an optimized glass fiber impregnation by the host polyester resin. Poor impregnation leads to void formation and reduced adhesion, leading to low surface quality. The adhesion level is clearly dependent on the sizing type applied to the surface of the glass fibers and on the matrix composition. Until now, research work has been focused on the effects of silane coupling agents on the interfacial interactions. However commercial glass fiber sizings are multi-component mixtures in which silane is only a little fraction of the total mass deposited on glass surface. A similar observation concerns the matrix.

This study considered the influence of chemical structure of two glass fiber sizings (A and B) on the impregnation of the fibers by an unsaturated polyester matrix before the curing reaction. The fibers were chosen to provide a low and a high surface quality respectively for fiber A and B for the final SMC part. Results give evidence of the various mechanisms occurring at the surface. The main parameters which should influence fiber impregnation are : i) the film former quantity, ii) the antistatic agent type, iii) the deposition method and iv) the nature of the film former. Therefore new sizing formulations were prepared to study these parameters in terms of adhesion provided by surface energies and to select some of them for molding. Thus, it has been possible to correlate fiber/matrix adhesion with SMC panel surface quality.

The surface energy approach is a useful additional tool to predict the surface quality of SMC panels before molding.

KEYWORDS : interphase, wetting, glass fiber sizing, SMC resin, surface aspect.

INTRODUCTION

A lot of researches have been conducted to give more information on the chemistry of the silanes and on the interactions between the glass fiber surface and the matrix [1] [2] [3] [4] [5] [6]. Nowadays, silanes represent a small fraction of the sizing system, which includes lubricants, film formers and antistatic agents. Extrapolations made with only the silane behavior on glass fiber /matrix adhesion neglect the potential effects of other sizing components on the glass fiber/matrix adhesion. To optimize SMC composites performances, the selection of materials for manufacturing fiber reinforced polymer composites must take into account not only the resin and the fiber, but also the type of reinforcement surface treatment (or sizing). The sizings have been shown to induce the formation of an interphase area, which affects the composite behavior [7] [8] [1,2 de CAR74]. This behavior can be influenced by the processing characteristics like viscosity, time to gelation, cure kinetics ...[9] [10] [11] [12] [13] [6]. Nevertheless, glass fiber/matrix adhesion could play an important role in the processing and on the surface quality of SMC composites. SMC processing requires the glass fibers to be well impregnated by the matrix. The more uniform and continuous the impregnation process, the better the surface properties of SMC. A poor impregnation will induce the formation of voids and will give a poor adhesion. This will generate defects on the SMC panel surface.

In the present work, we have studied the influence of the chemical structure of sizing on the impregnation with an unsaturated polyester matrix before the curing reaction and therefore on the surface quality of SMC panels. The influence of the sizing rate, the type of antistatic agents nature and their deposit method and of the polyester film formers nature were also studied.

MATERIALS AND TECHNIQUES

Materials:

Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 present the different sizings systems used for this study. For confidential reasons, just the antistatic agents and film formers nature are detailed. Sized glass fibers were developed and provided by Saint Gobain Vetrotex International (Chambéry, France). An industrial SMC resin paste was used.

Fiber	Sizing rate
1	1.38
2	1.59
3	1.79

Table 1. Different sizing rates.

Fiber	Antistatic agent	Deposit method
4	No	
5	quaternary ammonium chlorure	two steps
6	quaternary ammonium sulfate (type 1)	two steps
7	quaternary ammonium sulfate (type 1) + fluorated component	two steps
8	quaternary ammonium sulfate (type 2)	two steps
9	quaternary ammonium chlorure	one step
10	quaternary ammonium sulfate (type 1)	one step

Table 2. Different antistatic agents and their deposit method.

Fiber	Polyester	Antistatic agent	Deposit method
11	high unsaturated	none	
12	high unsaturated	quaternary ammonium sulfate / component fluorated	two steps
13	bisphenolic aromatic	none	
14	bisphenolic aromatic	quaternary ammonium sulfate / component fluorated	two steps
15	aromatic no bisphenolic	none	
16	aromatic no bisphenolic	quaternary ammonium sulfate / component fluorated	two steps

Table 3. Different film former polyester natures.

Techniques:

Contact-angle measurements of the sized glass fibers were performed using KSV LPR902 set-up (KSV Instruments). A scheme of the experimental setting is illustrated in figure 1. 9 mm length fibers were used. Samples were introduced into a glass cylinder (7 g). Contact-angle measurements of the SMC resin were performed using DIGIDROP apparatus (GBX Instruments), which allows an automatic formation of a liquid droplet on the SMC resin. Wetting liquids used for contact-angle measurements were n-hexane, water, toluene and ethylene glycol. The surface free energy (or surface tension) and other characteristics of the wetting liquids are listed in table 4.

Figure 1. Scheme of the experimental setting of KSV LPR902.

Wetting liquids	γ_L^D (a)	γ_L^P (b)	γ_L (c)	η (d)
n-hexane	18.40	0.00	18.40	0.29
water	21.80	51.00	72.80	1.00
ethylene glycol	29.30	19.00	48.30	13.76
toluene	26.10	2.30	28.40	0.52

Table 4. Characteristics of wetting liquids.

- (a) London dispersive component of free surface energy (mJ/m^2),
- (b) polar component of free surface energy (mJ/m^2),
- (c) total free surface energy (mJ/m^2),
- (d) viscosity ($\text{mPa}\cdot\text{s}$).

During the impregnation step, two phenomena should occur : wet-through and wet-out phenomena. The wet-through corresponds to the passage of the resin within the fibers network. Each filament is then progressively wetted. When the bundles break up the wet-out phenomenon occurs. In SMC applications, fibers used are relatively insoluble to keep good fiber integrity and a correct flow during the molding process. During the processing of SMC pre-pregs, the wet-through phenomenon should be favoured so that the resin go well through the fibers mat. Therefore, it can be assumed that the wet-through phenomenon is mainly governed by the mat permeability, which depends on physical parameters as fiber stiffness. A standard air permeabilimeter was adapted to evaluate the permeability of fiber mats (figure 2). A pump sucks up the air at an adjustable pression through the unit with defined circular openings. The sample of a known mass per unit area is put on the unit. The measured air flux (in $\text{l.s}^{-1}.\text{m}^{-2}$) corresponds to the permeability.

Figure 2. Scheme of the experimental setting of permeabilimeter.

The soluble fractions of the glass fiber coatings were measured according to ISO 11667 standard specifications [14]. A minimum of three samples was used for each determination. Extractions were carried on with acetone at room temperature during 24 h. The sizing solubility percentage was determined as follows :

$$TS\% = \frac{(P_0 - P_1)}{(P_0 - P_2)} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

with P_0 and P_1 corresponds to the mass of fibers before and after extraction and P_2 to the mass of fibers after calcination at $625 \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$ during 30 ± 5 min.

Saint-Gobain Vetrotex (Besana, Italia) provided SMC pre-pregs used in the present investigation. Glass fiber length is about 25 mm and weight ratio about 28%. In order to mold the tests specimens, a compression machine of Compositec (Rhône Alpesytem of 400 tons) was used and realized by Compositec (Le Bourget du Lac, France). The mold dimension was $500 \times 500 \text{ mm}^2$. The initial SMC charge was about 30% to obtain a 2 mm thick panel. The mold was equipped with polish optic punch. Temperatures were $150 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $145 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ respectively for fixed and mobile mold. The closure speed was 300 mm/s, the work speed was 7 mm/s. A holding pressure of 70 bars for 100 s was fixed. For each test 6 specimens were used to obtain revelant mean surface quality.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Contact-angle and free surface energy analyses

The contact angle, θ , was determined using Washburn's proposition, which defines the flow of a liquid through a capillary. Indeed when a porous solid is in contact with a liquid, the liquid rise between the solid pores is governed by :

$$T = \left[\frac{\eta}{C \cdot \gamma_L \cdot \cos \theta} \right] \cdot V^2 \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where T is the time after contact, η the liquid viscosity, C the material constant, γ_L the surface free energy of the liquid, θ the contact angle and V the liquid volume absorbed on the solid.

The slope of the $V^2 = f(\text{time})$ corresponds to $\eta/C \cdot \gamma_L \cdot \cos \theta$. Liquid viscosity and liquid free surface energy being known parameters, the contact angle and the material constant C are to be determined. Therefore, one measurement is provided for a contact angle near zero for small tension liquid to obtain the material constant C. The n-hexane would be an appropriate choice because of its surface tension of about $\gamma_L = 18.4 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ [15] [16] [CON11, CON17]. Same experiments with others liquids wetting solids were then investigated.

As concerns the determination of dispersive and polar components, geometric and harmonic approaches should be used. For this study, the geometric approach described by Owens et al. [17] [18] [4][5] was chosen in agreement with authors [19] [1] that have demonstrated that it is more representative and accurate most of the surface tension characteristics of liquids [20] [3 de CR-EMA]. Dispersive and polar components are determined as follows:

$$\gamma_L (1 + \cos \theta) = 2 \cdot (\gamma_S^D \cdot \gamma_L^D)^{1/2} + 2 \cdot (\gamma_S^P \cdot \gamma_L^P)^{1/2} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

where the subscripts L and S represent the liquid and solid states, respectively.

Equation 3 can be linearized $y = mx + b$ where :

$$x = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_L - \gamma_L^D}{\gamma_L^D}} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

$$y = \frac{1 + \cos \theta}{2} \cdot \frac{\gamma_L}{\sqrt{\gamma_L^D}} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

$$m = \sqrt{\gamma_S^P} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

$$b = \sqrt{\gamma_S^D} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

If γ_L , γ_L^D , γ_L^P are known parameters for all wetting liquids through literature and if the solid surface contact angle has been measured, dispersive and polar components of the solid can be determined. Glass fibers can be considered as small energy solids. The dispersive component γ_S^D characterizes the surface capacity to develop Van der Waals interfacial interactions. In order to obtain more detailed and precise information about the fiber/matrix interactions, the free surface energy and the dispersive, polar components of the SMC resin were also determined. Then optimal interactions occur if :

- 1) the fiber γ_S component is superior to the SMC resin γ_S one ; more the difference between these two energies is great, better is the wetting,
- 2) a good adhesion is obtained when the dispersive and polar components of the fiber and the SMC resin are equivalent,

Thus, the influence of the sizing rate, the type of antistatic agents nature and their deposit method and of the polyester film formers nature were also studied.

1.1. Influence of the sizing rate (fibers 1, 2, 3)

To increase the sizing rate, the percentage of film former has been changed. Other components are the same. The results are given in the figure 3. It can be observed that the free surface energy is equivalent for the three fibers. Nevertheless, an increase of the dispersive component and a decrease of the polar component with the sizing rate increasing have been shown. Therefore, the fiber/matrix adhesion should be improved for high sizing rate. It must be notified that these data do not take into account the evolution of the sizing dissolution phenomenon and it is only representative of this formula.

1.2. Influence of the antistatic agent nature (fibers 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8)

The results (figure 4) show an increase of the free surface energy when an antistatic agent is applied on the sizing fiber. According to the antistatic agent nature, the free surface energy varies as follows : fiber 7 < fiber 5 \approx fiber 6 < fiber 8. The fiber dispersive, polar components depend on the antistatic agent nature. The quaternary ammonium sulfate type 1 (fiber 6) gives a dispersive character to the fiber surface. Other antistatic agents give polar character (fibers 5, 7 and 8). The fiber/matrix adhesion should be enhanced when the quaternary ammonium sulfate type 1 antistatic agent is used. Moreover even if the adhesion between the fiber without antistatic agent (fiber 4) and the resin is available, an antistatic agent remains useful for the fiber cutting.

1.3. Influence of the deposit method of the antistatic agent (fibers 4, 5, 6, 9 and 10)

The antistatic agent can be deposited on glass fibers in one step by being introduced directly in size solution or in two steps by being deposited on the already sized fibers. Figure 5 shows the influence of the deposit method on free surface energy measurements. The same behavior was observed for the fiber without any antistatic agent (fiber 4) and the fiber coated in one step by a quaternary ammonium chlorure (fiber 9).

Elsewhere the introduction in one step of quaternary ammonium sulfate (fiber 10) increases the free surface energy and polar component. The influence of the deposit method can be studied by comparing the fibers 5 and 9 on one hand and 6 and 10 on the other hand. The best wetting is observed for quaternary ammonium chlorure deposited in two steps and for quaternary sulfate ammonium deposited in one step. For a good adhesion, contrary behaviour should be obtained.

1.4. Influence of the polyester film former nature (fibers 11, 12, 13, 14, 15 and 16)

Figure 6 shows that the presence of an antistatic agent increases the free surface energy except when a bisphenolic aromatic polyester is used as film former (fiber 14). Moreover, the presence of aromatic polyester increases the polar component (fiber 15) and a high-unsaturated polyester increases the dispersive component (fiber 11). It can be shown that the antistatic agent role is not negligible; the interactions between the antistatic agent and the aromatic polyester, and the high-unsaturated polyester enhance respectively the dispersive and the polar parameter of the fiber. Best wetting and best adhesion should both be obtained for fibers 11 and 16. So that it seems to be difficult to conclude about the variations of free surface energies according to the sizings. The fiber permeability has been measured.

Figure 3. Influence of sizing rate

Figure 4. Influence of the antistatic agent nature

Figure 5. Influence of the antistatic agent deposit method

Figure 6. Influence of the film former polyester nature

2. Permeability measurements

The permeability measurement is a good tool to predict the wet through of the fibers and is an important parameter in the processing of the SMC pre pregs. Figure 7 shows that the fiber permeability is different according to the sizing nature. It can be observe that even if the glass fiber surface behavior suggests that both a good wetting and a good adhesion occur, no evident correlation can be carried on for the SMC pre pregs. For example, the fiber 6, that should be well impregnated by the resin, presents a poor permeability. Fiber 14 that presents high permeability may not be well impregnated. Therefore a compromise between wettability and permeability is necessary. The best compromise is obtained with the fibers 11 and 16 as these fibers have better wetting and permeability. Thus, fibers 11 and 16 could be used for the manufacturing of SMC pre-pregs.

3. Compression molding

After molding, the surface quality was evaluated by using a Diffracto Sight AS-2 (Diffracto Ltd). Results are presented in figure 8. The surface quality is better when the Diffracto index is low so that fiber 7 is the best. Relationships between Diffracto index and the different measured parameters (free surface energy, solubility, stiffness, permeability) were determined (figure 9). To optimize the surface quality of molded SMC panels the following conditions are required :

- a medium solubility (~ 65 %) of the sizing
- a low permeability (~ 800 L/s/m²)
- a high fiber stiffness (~ 140 mm)

No evident relationship with free surface energy was revealed.

The surface quality is also defined by the other defects like pinholes, bubbles and craters. Relationships between the defect numbers were determined (figures 10, 11 and 12). None pinhole is obtained with the following fiber characteristics :

- a low solubility (~ 30 %) of the sizing
- a high permeability (~ 1000 L/s/m²)
- a high fiber stiffness (~ 140 mm)
- a high free surface energy (~ 30 mJ/m²)

Moreover, a direct relationship with free surface energy was revealed. None pinhole is obtained with a fiber having a good wetting (fiber 16).

None bubble and few craters are obtained if the fiber characteristics are :

- a medium solubility (~ 65 %) of the sizing
- a low permeability (~ 800 L/s/m²)
- a high fiber stiffness (~ 140 mm)
- a high free surface energy (~ 30 mJ/m²)

It appears necessary to have a compromise between the fiber characteristics to provide a SMC panel with a good Diffracto index and without defects (pinholes, bubbles and craters).

Figure 7. Permeability of the fibers

Figure 8. Evaluation of the SMC panels surface quality.

Figure 9. Influence of the parameters on Diffraction index.

Figure 10. Influence of the parameters on pinholes number.

Figure 11. Influence of the parameters on bubbles number.

Figure 12. Influence of the parameters on craters number.

CONCLUSIONS

The sizing solubility, the mat permeability, the fiber free surface energy and the glass fiber stiffness are key parameters as regards the SMC impregnation process. These parameters vary with the sizing rate, the antistatic agent nature and its deposit method, and of the film former polyester nature. Nevertheless, a compromise between all the fiber characteristics is required. For a good surface quality, the glass fiber must have a high stiffness, a medium solubility, a high free surface energy and a low permeability as it summarized in table 5. It can be concluded that a good tool to predict the surface quality has been developed. It allows better understanding oh the impregnation level of the glass fiber by the resin.

Fibers characteristics	good Surface	none pinholes	none bubbles / few craters
Permeability	low	high	low
Stiffness	high	high	high
Free surface energy	-	high	high
Solubility	medium	low	medium

Table 5. Summary of the results

- 1 H. Al Moussawi, E. K. Drown and L. T. Dzral, "The silane/sizing composite interphase", *Polymer Composites*, 1993, vol. 14, n°3, pp. 195-200.
- 2 K. Tsutsumi and T. Ohsuga, "Surface characterization of modified glass fibers by inverse chromatography", *Colloid and Polymer Science*, 1990, vol. 268, pp. 38-44.
- 3 H. J. Barraza, M. J. Hwa, K. Blakey, E. A. O'Rear, and B. P. Grady, "Wetting behavior of elastomer-modified glass fibers", *Langmuir*, 2001, vol. 17, pp. 5288-5296.
- 4 S-J. Park, T-J. Kim, "Studies on surface energetics of glass fabrics in an unsaturated polyester matrix system: effect of sizing treatment on glass fabrics", *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 2001, vol. 80, pp. 1439-1445.
- 5 P. Gao, K. B. Su, Y. Ward, L. T. Weng, "Effects of chemical composition and thermal stability of finishes on the compatibility between glass fiber and high melting temperature thermoplastics", *Polymer Composites*, 2000, vol. 21, n°2, pp. 312-321.
- 6 J. L. Thomason, "The interface region in glass fibre-reinforced epoxy resin composites : 3. Characterization of fibre surface coatings and the interphase", *Composites*, 1995, vol. 26, n°7, pp. 487-498.
- 7 G. R. Palmese, R. L. McCullough, *Journal of Adhesion*, 1994, vol. 44, pp. 29
- 8 T. P. Skourlis, R. L. McCullough, *Composite Science and Technology*, 1993, vol. 49, pp. 363.
- 9 B. K. Larson and L. T. Dzral, "Glass fibre sizing/matrix interphase formation in liquid composite moulding: effects on fibre/matrix adhesion and mechanical properties", *Composite*, 1994, vol. 25, n°7, pp. 711-721.
- 10 J. L. Thomason, « The interface region in glass-reinforced epoxy rein composites : 1. Sample preparation, void content and interfacial strength", *Composites*, 1995, vol. 26, n°7, pp. 467-475.
- 11 E. K. Drown, H. Al Moussawi and L. T. Dzral, "Glass fiber 'sizings' and their role in fiber-matrix adhesion", *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, 1991, vol. 5, n°10, pp. 865-881.
- 12 G.R. Palmese, O. A. Andersen, V. M. Karbhari, „Effect of glass fiber sizing on the cure kinetics of vinyl-ester resins“, *Composites: Part A*, 1999, vol. 30, pp. 11-18.

-
- 13 R.L. Gorowara, W. E. Kosik, S. C. McKnight, R. L. McCullough, "Molecular characterization of glass fiber surface coatings for thermosetting polymer matrix/glass fiber composites", *Composites: Part A*, 2001, vol. 32, pp. 323-329.
- 14 Norme ISO 11667 : 1997, Plastiques renforcés de fibre – Préimprégnés et compositions de moulage – Détermination des taux de résine, de fibre de renfort et de charge minérale – Méthodes par dissolution, 1997.
- 15 H-J. Jacobash, K. Grundke, E. Mäder, K-H .Freitag and U. Panzer, "Application of the surface free energy concept in polymer processing", *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, 1992, vol.6, n°12, pp. 1381-1396.
- 16 K. Tsutsumi, Y. Abe, "Determination of dispersive and nondispersive components of the surface free energy of glass fibers", *Colloid and Polymer Science*, 1989, vol. 267, pp. 637-642.
- 17 D. K. Owens and R. C. Wendt, "Estimation of the surface free energy of polymers", *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 1969, vol. 13, p. 1741-1747.
- 18 J. Gonzalez-Benito, J. Baselga, A. J. Aznar, "Microstructural and wettability study of surface pretreated glass fibres", *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 1999, vol. 92-93, p. 129-134.
- 19 P. Dalet, E. Papon and J-J. Villenave, "Surface free energy of polymeric materials : relevancy of conventional contact angle data analyses", *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, 1999, vol. 13, n° 8, p. 857-870.
- 20 R. J. Good, in *Contact angle, Wettability and Adhesion*, K. L. Mittal (Ed.), VSP, Utrecht, The Netherlands, p. 3, 1993.